

Table 1. Silvershoots in GM resistance trials. Bihar, India, 1984-86.

Variety	Silvershoots ^a (%)			
	1984	1985	1986	Mean ^b
Kalamdani	2.13 (4.54)	1.00 (1.00)	3.23 (10.43)	2.13 (4.54) c
Baghpanjar	1.83 (3.35)	1.60 (2.56)	0.60 (0.36)	1.34 (1.80) ab
Bhojni	2.73 (7.45)	1.20 (1.44)	2.63 (6.92)	2.20 (4.08) c
Saraikelela	0.87 (0.76)	1.77 (3.13)	2.63 (6.92)	1.76 (3.10) bc
Dhusri	3.13 (9.80)	1.73 (3.00)	3.63 (13.18)	2.83 (8.00) d
Karnusal	2.97 (8.82)	2.13 (4.54)	4.50 (20.25)	3.30 (9.18) de
Bheri-rice	3.03 (9.18)	1.37 (1.88)	3.13 (9.80)	2.51 (6.30) cd
Jaya (susceptible check)	4.37 (19.10)	3.20 (10.24)	4.63 (21.44)	4.07 (16.60) e
RD202 (resistant check)	1.10 (1.21)	1.40 (1.96)	0.60 (0.36)	1.03 (1.06) a
Shakti (resistant check)	2.10 (4.41)	0.63 (0.40)	1.50 (2.25)	1.41 (2.00) ab
CD (0.05)	0.89	1.15	0.86	0.93

^aFigures in parentheses = original values. ^bValues followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Table 2. Yield in GM resistance trial. Bihar, India, 1984-86.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)			
	1984	1985	1986	Mean ^a
Kalamdani	4.3	1.2	2.1	2.5
Baghpanjar	2.4	1.5	3.3	2.4
Bhojni	3.7	0.7	2.8	2.4
Saraikelela	2.6	1.5	2.8	2.3
Dhusri	3.7	1.4	2.9	2.7
Karnusal	3.3	0.6	2.8	2.2
Bheri-rice	3.0	0.8	2.4	2.1
Jaya	4.0	1.2	2.9	2.7
RD202	3.6	1.2	2.5	2.5
Shakti	2.6	0.8	3.8	2.4

Adverse soils tolerance

Growth recovery from salt stress during initial seedling stage

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In the southern and eastern part of India near the sea, the rice crop is affected by tides at the early seedling stage. We studied the effect of salinity on seedling growth after removal of salt stress.

The experiment was conducted in petri dishes at electrical conductivity (EC) of 1.5 and 13.6 dS/m. Forty seeds each of Jaya (tolerant) and Basmati 370 (sensitive) varieties were placed in petri dishes lined with filter paper Whatman No. 1, with 30 replications. Seeds were surface-sterilized by 0.1% mercuric chloride solution.

Salinity stress was removed 4, 6, and 8 d after sowing (DAS) by washing 10 replications/treatment with water at EC 1.5 dS/m. Two replications were removed at each sampling to measure length of root, shoot, dry weight of root and shoot, endosperm part, and recovery rate.

Salinity retarded root and shoot

Carryover effect of salinity at seedling stage on root and shoot length after stress removal, Ludhiana, India. Arrows indicate days when stress was removed.

growth. On removal of salt stress, seedlings began to recover.

Initial recovery in root and shoot length was better when stress was

removed 4 DAS. Jaya gained more than Basmati 370 (see figure).

Root and shoot weight decreased with salinity and the recovery gap widened with days under stress. Salinity caused less decrease in endosperm weight due to decreased metabolic mobilization. Seed weight decreased more in Jaya than in Basmati 370 (see table).

Salinity appeared to retard root and shoot growth more on Basmati 370 than on Jaya. Recovery also was better in Jaya. High initial recovery rate in Jaya was accompanied by less dry weight decrease of endosperm, showing more hydrolysis and translocation of metabolite from endosperm. This indicated that longer stress might cause irreversible effects on metabolism. Jaya's faster recovery may be due to higher metabolic utilization from the endosperm. □

Effect of salinity on endosperm utilization rate (% seed weight decrease/5 seeds) on recovery from salt stress.^a Ludhiana, India.

Salinity (dS/m)	Day of stress removal	Variety	Endosperm utilization rate at given time (d) after germination						
			4 d	6 d	8 d	10 d	12 d	14 d	16 d
1.5	<i>Seed weight (%)</i>								
		Jaya	0.0	30.5 (30.5)	41.2 (15.3)	62.5 (36.5)	65.6 (7.8)	66.0 (2.3)	66.6 (0.6)
		Basmati 370	0.0	9.7 (9.7)	36.7 (29.9)	48.9 (19.1)	57.5 (16.8)	64.1 (15.5)	63.7 (1.2)
13.6	<i>Recovery from stress</i>								
	4	Jaya	0.0	7.5 (7.5)	24.3 (18.2)	51.6 (35.9)	59.6 (16.6)	—	—
		Basmati 370	0.0	2.5 (2.5)	22.1 (20.1)	38.7 (21.3)	51.1 (20.1)	—	—
	6	Jaya	—	0.0	11.3 (11.3)	25.4 (15.8)	48.3 (30.6)	62.2 (27.2)	—
		Basmati 370	—	0.0	13.0 (13.0)	25.1 (13.9)	38.9 (18.9)	47.7 (14.4)	—
	8	Jaya	—	—	0.0	19.5 (19.5)	29.8 (12.8)	39.0 (13.1)	59.7 (33.9)
		Basmati 370	—	—	0.0	8.3 (8.3)	20.1 (12.9)	34.2 (17.6)	45.3 (16.9)

^a Values in parentheses indicate increase over time interval.

Effect of salinity on net assimilation and rice grain yield

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We studied the critical limits of salt tolerance and the effects of salinity on net assimilation rate (NAR) of M1-48, Jaya, CST-202-2, CST-438-1, CST-14-2, CST-100-1, and CSR-1 rice varieties. M1-48 and CSR-1 were the salt-sensitive and salt-tolerant checks. Jaya and the CST genotypes have been found promising in coastal saline soils.

Three salinity levels — ECe 4.0, 8.0, and 12.0 dS/m — were created artificially by adding saline river water. At 25 °C, average composition of river water at 35 dS/m was 7571.3 Na, 269.2 K, 403.8 Ca, 778.0 Mg, 1314.3 Cl, 969.1 ppm SO₄, and pH 7.8.

Thirty-day-old seedlings were transplanted in 20-kg capacity porcelain pots, 4 plants/pot, with 4 replications. Fertilizer was applied at 120 kg N, 26.4 kg P, 49.8 kg K/ha as urea, single superphosphate, and muriate of potash.

Effect of salinity levels (3, 8, 12 dS/m) on grain yield and NAR of 7 varieties. Parganas, India.

Variety	Grain yield (g/plant)			NAR at peak tillering (g/plant per wk)		
	3.0	8.0	12.0	3.0	8.0	12.0
M1-48	17.1	10.3	Nil	3.24	0.51	0.06
Jaya	14.4	12.3	11.7	3.08	1.55	1.08
CST-202-2	32.6	21.8	10.7	1.47	1.01	0.16
CST-438-1	22.1	20.7	8.7	3.04	0.60	0.08
CST-14-2	28.5	23.3	15.2	3.24	2.10	1.80
CST-100-1	21.6	21.6	9.6	1.81	1.36	0.76
CSR-1	31.8	29.5	13.0	1.81	2.00	1.09
CD at P = 0.05						
	Varieties: 2.67			0.13		
	Salinity: 1.74			0.08		
	Var. × Sal: 4.62			0.22		

CST-14-2 had the highest grain yield at ECe 12 dS/m, followed by CSR-1 (see table). At peak tillering, NAR was significantly reduced in all genotypes

with increase in soil salinity. This reduction was least in CST-14-2. CST-14-2 and CSR-1 are the more tolerant of the genotypes tested. □

Integrated germplasm improvement

Improved rice varieties released in Nigeria

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Five NCRI breeding lines belonging to three crosses (Table 1) were recently released as FARO 30 to 34. Three medium-duration ITA lines were released as FARO 35 to 37. The